

Natural History and Circulation of Knowledge in the Writing of Friar João dos Santos (Eastern Africa, 1586–1609)

MORENO STEDILE

MA Student, University of São Paulo

Abstract

*This paper has as its main thread a case study on Friar João dos Santos' *Etiópia Oriental*, acknowledging its relevance and singularity as regards the production of knowledge about Eastern Africa observed on the trajectory of the book since its publication in 1609 to the present day, in Iberian or African studies. From the analysis of textual forms of epistemic validation, we have been able to observe the meanings of knowledge that comes from experience in the Early Modern Period, especially concerning the knowledge that articulates cartography, natural history and travel literature. This reflection leads to the production of knowledge connecting metropolitan centres to the frontiers of maritime Empires, which reveals dynamics that are characteristic of contact zones and regimes of circulation related to imperial networks. From the Dominican missionary's biodiversity descriptions, mainly the depictions of African animals, we have been able to observe the multiple forms of local agency and engagement that have combined in the production of such knowledge. We have also sought to observe the local networks in which the Dominican is embedded; who his informants are, and the negotiated dimension of this movement. This has led us to investigate the modes of mediation, translation, and the possibilities of using a European source to apprehend African interests, perspectives, and knowledge; with a view to understanding these subjects not as passive informants, but as active agents who negotiate their forms of engagement and imprint their mark upon the production of scientific knowledge.*

Keywords: Travel Literature – Natural History – Eastern Africa – Early Modern Period – History of Science

Introduction and Methodology

The “Scientific Revolution” was a powerful historiographic narrative crystallized in the Western *curriculum* in the first half of the twentieth century. Differently from “the Renaissance” or “modernity,” concepts that existed from the sixteenth century onwards, the notion of “revolution” at that time was more related to the cyclic conception present in the work *The revolutionibus orbium coelestium* (1545) by Copernicus. With the rise of cultural studies and criticism in the 1980s, the whole idea of a “Scientific Revolution” was rejected as a “grand narrative” of the West. The notion of “science” itself was put under suspicion. This criticism gave way to a proliferation of case studies, giving rise to the necessity of reevaluating the level of the local production of knowledge, and the aspects of its circulation. In addition, social, material and literary practices that surrounded knowledge production became objects of study. The notions of a centre and a periphery were reevaluated, as well as the dichotomy colonizer-colonized, emphasising the necessity of understanding local forms of mediation, negotiation and translation, situated in their social, economic and cultural patterns.³²⁴

This paper builds on these developments of historical research, having as its main thread a case study on Friar João dos Santos’ work, *Etiópia Oriental e Varia História de Cousas Notáveis do Oriente*, in particular his depictions of natural history regarding African animals, which remained the more important source, under the corpus of European sources, in that field until the late nineteenth century. The role of those depictions in his work (a huge publication from the Dominican Convent from Evora, printed in the year 1609) is related to the connections between natural history and travel literature in the early modern period. Since it is not a scientific treaty, but a book that organizes from a cartographic perspective (at least in the first volume) a diversified collection of experiences and knowledge locally gathered during the author’s stay in Eastern Africa, from 1586 to 1597, and later in Goa until 1600. As characteristic of travel literature in that period, it draws on the fields of religion, ethnography, commercial information, political history, curiosities, etc. The Dominican friar presents the work as a result of his “eye-witness testimonies,” a result of the eleven years he lived on the African continent, which would assure the “credit” of that knowledge.³²⁵

³²⁴ Federico Palomo, “Production et circulation des savoirs dans une monarchie polycentrique: Goa, la chrétienté éthiopienne et l’empire portugais du XVIIe siècle,” *Annales. Histoire, Sciences Sociales*, 78 (2022): 429, 430; Antonio Sanchez Martinez, “La ‘Atlantización’ de la ciencia ibérica: el mundo atlántico visto desde la historia de la temprana ciencia moderna,” *Anuario de Estudios Atlánticos* 60 (2014); Fa-ti Fan, “The Global Turn in the History of Science,” *East Asian Science, Technology and Society: An International Journal* 6 (2012).

³²⁵ João dos Santos, *Etiópia oriental e varia história de cousas notáveis do Oriente*, (Lisbon: Biblioteca dos Clássicos Portugueses: 1891 [1609]), 40.

New perspectives of the history of science and modernity lead to a reflection on the local production of knowledge, the role and “activities of various intermediaries, brokers, go-betweens and translators, without whom the colonial institutions or the religious orders could have successfully interacted with the local communities, nor gained access to their set of practices and knowledge.”³²⁶ We have observed how the status of “eyewitness testimony” is extended to other subjects, and those who are considered “credible people” are not necessarily European. Actually, knowledge production happens through networks that surpass cultural boundaries. The origin of these individuals could come from an “extreme diverse cosmos, with varied cultural, religious and linguistic backgrounds, building many dimensions of sociability, sharing knowledge and other cultural features.”³²⁷ For example, on the religious matter, João dos Santos affirms having interrogated “honorable kaffirs” on their notions of God and creation.³²⁸ Elsewhere, he refers to having been cured from a sickness by a Muslim woman from the Quirimbas, who is referred to as a “great master.”³²⁹ The stories told by people considered “credible” permeate the entire work of João dos Santos, fitting into a movement of much more fluid circulation between writing, imagery, and orality, which were not yet hierarchized as they later would be in the eighteenth century. In truth, “memory” continued to be the primary form of knowledge in the early modern period. The local collecting of information emphasizes the transcultural character of the knowledge produced in colonial territories.

While living in Goa, João dos Santos got in touch with members of the intellectual environment to which Garcia Orta had previously belonged. Studies have asserted the Dominican’s relation to Goa’s erudite circles, namely his relation to Diogo do Couto, who held an important library in the capital of the Portuguese State of India.³³⁰ It was an important centre for the circulation and concentration of knowledge from all around the Indian Ocean, since the Portuguese networks, along with many religious orders, went from Eastern Africa to China and up to Japan. Returning to Portugal, João dos Santos wrote his work under the auspices of the Dominican Convent of Évora, his hometown. The publication of the book resulted in his return to Africa, as chief of a mission to what was believed to be the silver mines of Chicova, near Tete, up the Zambezi River. Many other works were consulted to write the book, in libraries in Goa, Lisbon and Évora. Particularly, the Dominican refers to other travellers, who could give fresh and consistent information, based on experience. This paper concentrates its analysis on the first three

³²⁶ Amelia Polónia et al., eds., *Cross-Cultural Exchange and the Circulation of Knowledge in the First Global Age* (Porto: CIHCEM, 2018), 7.

³²⁷ Polónia et al., *Cross-cultural Exchange*, 7.

³²⁸ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 70.

³²⁹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, vol 2., 245.

³³⁰ Rui Manuel Loureiro, *A biblioteca de Diogo do Couto* (Macau: Instituto Cultural, 1998).

books of *Etiópia oriental*, which offer an account of the author's personal contribution, from his personal experience as a missionary in Eastern Africa.

Early Modern Knowledge

This form of validating the knowledge produced by the author's "eye-witness testimonies" draws on the notion of "experience" from the early modern period. Differently from the Middle Ages, when the eyes, and generally, the external senses, were discredited as misleading (when true knowledge came from the Bible and the Church authorities), one of the characteristics of the modern period was a reshaping of human vision as a category of cognition. This was not incompatible with a religious vision of the world, or with a Catholic cosmivision;³³¹ on the contrary, Adam's myth was reevaluated in the Renaissance, combined with Prometheus', recognizing in each man, one reflection of God's image, God's capacity of creation.³³² Particularly, Iberian knowledge in modern times put even the Classics' authority into question. Strong ideas from classic authors were debunked, such as the torrid zone, its inhabitability and navigability, and the existence of antipodes, besides the discovery of a whole new continent (America) and the Southern Hemisphere with its new constellations. This consciousness was expressed in a letter by Italian scholar Tommaso Campanella, which recognises that authorities such as Saint Augustine were turned into "liars [*buggiardi*]" by a "simple mariner" [*un mariano*] with his "eye-witness testimonies [*testimoniari de visú*]."³³³

The first consciousness of superiority of the moderns over the ancients was forged in the Iberian Peninsula in the sixteenth century, as per authors such as José Antonio Maravall, from Spain, and José Sebastião da Silva Dias, from Portugal.³³⁴ Nevertheless, these catholic roots of modernity were obscured by the grand narrative of the "Scientific Revolution" that emphasised Protestant and northern European trajectories in the shaping of modern knowledge.³³⁵ Such consciousness is particularly expressed in Portugal by Garcia Orta, and others from his generation, in his important work *Colloquies on the Simples and Drugs from India*, first published in 1563. This work

³³¹ Traditional sociologic and historical approaches of European history have emphasised the differences between rationalism in the protestant North and religious thought in the Catholic South. Newer approaches tend to relativise such dichotomy, understanding that a Catholic worldview was not incompatible with scientific thought, on the contrary, Italy and the Iberian Peninsula continued to be important centres of knowledge production and diffusion, even to Elizabethan England.

³³² Ernst Cassirer, *O indivíduo e o cosmos na filosofia do Renascimento* (São Paulo: Martins fontes, 2001).

³³³ Quoted in José Sebastião da Silva Dias. *Os descobrimentos e a problemática cultural do século XVI* (Lisbon: Presença, 1962), 119.

³³⁴ José Antonio Maravall, *Antiguos y modernos* (Madrid: Sociedade de Estudios y Publicaciones, 1966); Silva Dias, *Os descobrimentos e a problemática cultural do século XVI*.

³³⁵ Jorge Cañizares-Esguerra, *Nature, Empire and Nation: Explorations of the History of Science in the Iberian World* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2006).

is an important example of the role of Iberian knowledge and its circulation in modern Europe. It was successively republished in Antwerp, in 1567, 1582, 1586 and 1593, twice translated and published into Latin, in 1582 and 1593, not to mention Italian (1595) and French (1619), in a fifty-year interval following its publication – a best-seller from the period that Benedict Anderson called “print-capitalism.”³³⁶

In terms of publications, other Portuguese works from the time have followed the same path, as shown by Silva Dias. Fernão Lopes de Castanheda’s history from India, published in 1551, was translated into French (1553), German (1565), and English (1582). Fernão Mendes Pinto’s travel book, called *Peregrinações* – revealing information from all parts of the world visited or not by the author – was also widely translated. Similar to other Portuguese authors João dos Santos’ work would have a significant of European translations, which will be exposed at the end of this article. Travel literature was a successful editorial genre in the Early modern period. Take, for example, Hans Staden’s *True History* of his travels to Brazil. Despite not being an Iberian author, he gives an account of experiences that took place in Portuguese America. They were first published in German and translated into many languages and successively republished, along with the original prints that revealed scenes of cannibalism among the Tupinamba.³³⁷

Garcia da Orta is an important author because of the consciousness he expresses of modern notions of knowledge through experience, as well as for having taken to India his project of natural history knowledge-gathering, collaborating with local interlocutors in Goa, where he kept an important botanic garden in the middle of the sixteenth century. It is important for our purpose to understand Orta’s thought because he and his generation directly inspired the kind of erudition expressed later by João dos Santos. In early modern Europe, natural history was comprised not only of fauna, flora and minerals (as in the latter Enlightenment notion), but also of medical knowledge, therapeutic uses of the natural world, which could include even miraculous sources. Orta expresses the continuation of a field of natural history shaped in Portugal by Amato Lusitano, who collected in the markets of Lisbon plants and spices from different parts of the world, registering and researching their uses. Connected to the more radical humanist movement in Portugal, Amato Lusitano, a *cristão-novo* (“new-Christian”), publicly returned to Judaism and fled to the Netherlands in 1559. Orta took that project to India. In his *Colloquies*, organised as a dialogue

³³⁶ In the first chapter of “Imagined Communities,” Benedict Anderson defines “print-capitalism” as the editorial boom that followed the invention of the press and the many possibilities it opens, which according to him played an important role in the rise of national identities and State, in the Renaissance and the Reformation, and the transformations that characterised modern era. Benedict Anderson, *Imagined Communities: Reflection on the Origins and Spread of Nationalism* (London: Verso, 1983), 9-37.

³³⁷ Silva Dias, *Os descobrimentos*, 107; Luciana Villas-Boas, *Encontros escritos: semântica histórica do Brasil colonial* (Rio de Janeiro: Editora UFRJ, 2017).

where he opposes two characters: Dr Ruano and Dr. Orta. The prior, a former student from Salamanca and a typical erudite with a trove of memorised quotations from classic authors the latter, Dr. Orta himself, the practical man, traveller and observer, who founds knowledge on experience. Orta says to his interlocutor:

“Do not scare me with Dioscorides or Galen, because I will not say anything except the truth and what I know. (...) I will not say anything is good unless it is witnessed by my own eyes [testemunho de vista] or trustworthy people [pessoas de crédito]. (...) As a witness of my own eyes [testemunho de vista], although lower than all the doctors, I will be given more faith than those priests of Greek medicine who wrote based on false information.”³³⁸

João dos Santos, when introducing his book and supporting his arguments, directly incorporates this passage from Orta, emphasizing that everything he was going to say was a result of his “eye-witness testimony” [*testemunho de vista*] or told by “trustworthy-people” [*pessoas de crédito*]. Despite the Dominicans being the managers of the Inquisition in Portugal, João dos Santos reveals his relations with the canons of Portuguese humanism, quoting passages from Orta, and even from more radical Amato Lusitano, who was already censored at the time and is briefly quoted in the second volume. Also, D. João de Castro, the Viceroy of India, is brought up as an exemplar historic character in the Dominican’s narrative. Beside Orta and Lusitano, the Viceroy was another canon of the time of king. João III. In a letter written from Mozambique to the king in August 1538, Castro reveals having used the shadow instrument developed by cosmographer Pedro Nunes to take measures from different parts of the Indian ocean, its latitudes, while also taking notes on the sea currents, winds, and, particularly, on animals from the sea and land.³³⁹ In *Etiópia Oriental*, D. João de Castro is remembered as a “prudent captain,”³⁴⁰ not for any military action or conquest, but the example evoked by his good administration consists in discovering through experience the real cause of the redness of parts of the Red Sea. In the book, after considering many theories about the origin of that name, from classic authors, such as Aristotle and Pliny, João dos Santos asserts that “all these opinions (despite coming from such grave authors), were refuted and dismissed with the following [opinion] secured, corrected and *verified through experience*.”³⁴¹ This verified opinion belonged to the Viceroy, which is quoted from his *Geographic Commentaries* and said

³³⁸ Quoted in Silva Dias. *Os descobrimentos*, 97, 98 [translated].

³³⁹ Silva Dias, *Os descobrimentos*.

³⁴⁰ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 465.

³⁴¹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 464, 465, highlights added for emphasis [original: “todas estas opiniões (posto que sejam de tão graves autores) se podem refutar, e desfazer com a seguinte, segura, correta e verificada pela experiência”].

to have wandered different parts of the Red Sea, sending divers to collect material from the bottom, replicating this experience in different parts of the Sea.³⁴²

João dos Santos: a Dominican Traveller in Eastern Africa

Following the example of figures such as Orta and Castro, João dos Santos put his effort into producing knowledge during his trip and missionary work in Eastern Africa. This knowledge is organised in a way of writing that is typical of the travel literature of that time, which combined different literary genres and a particular kind of exoticism. Basing the validity of his writing on experience, the author emphasizes the locally-gathered dimension of the knowledge, constantly bringing up his travel experiences. His travel itinerary is the guiding line of the narrative, that is organized in a cartographic way. The narrative begins with his departure from Lisbon, in 1586, answering the Bishop of Malaca's call for missionaries to the Indian Ocean. Arriving in Mozambique, his first mission was to serve as a clerk in the church of Sofala, responsible, as he put it, for "600 confessing souls, comprised of Portuguese, *mestiços*, and people of the land".³⁴³ This passage already exhibits the transcultural networks in which the Dominican is embedded. Sofala was an ancient Swahili port in the mouth of the Buzi River, long recognised in Arabian cartography as the main source of gold in the Indian ocean trade. This trade was related to the connections developed by the Swahili with the Shona societies from the hinterland.³⁴⁴ The first book of *Etiópia oriental* is dedicated to Sofala, its hinterland, comprising a description of the societies, people, mores, the history of Portuguese presence, trade information, as well as many animal depictions.

Even though the gold trade there still existed, in the sixteenth century a major part of it was diverted to the route of the Zambezi River, accessing directly, through the cities of Sena and Tete, in the Botonga territory on the margins of that river, the Zimbabwe plateau, where the main gold bazaars were located, namely in the Mwenemutapa, which was recognized at the time as the great African kingdom from the hinterland. João dos Santos took that route in 1590, reaching the city of Tete in 1591.³⁴⁵ The second book of his work describes the Zambezi valley and the Zimbabwean plateau; this is a very relevant part of his work, because it was the first erudite description of the interior of Central-Eastern Africa, and lasted for a long time as one of the main sources of information to Europeans about that land.³⁴⁶ David Livingstone, in the nineteenth

³⁴² Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 465.

³⁴³ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 46. "600 almas de confissão, em que entravam portugueses, mestiços e gente da terra."

³⁴⁴ Maylin Newitt. *History of Mozambique*. (London: Hurst, 1995).

³⁴⁵ S. I. G. Mudenge, *A political history of Munhumutapa*. (Harare: Zimbabwean Press, 1988).

³⁴⁶ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 163–256.

century, would still follow the Dominican's path, travelling through the Zambezi and reaching the plateau through Tete.³⁴⁷ Again, in this book, different literary genres and topics are combined: many chapters are dedicated to the mores of the Mwenemutapa, from political protocols to religious information. Trade routes and the presence of Portuguese and *mestizo* communities are also described. Besides that, João dos Santos does not omit the depiction of animals, talking about the animals from the river and the hinterlands.

Later in 1592, João dos Santos was redesignated as a clerk in the church of Ibo, an island in the Quirimbas archipelago, south of the Rovuma River, on the northern shore of contemporary Mozambique. This was a complex of 31 islands along the shore of the African continent, divided by short intervals of sea and mangrove. In the third book of his work, the Dominican describes the Portuguese presence along the chain of islands and their interaction with the Swahili Muslim community.³⁴⁸ This presence was mostly related to the ivory trade from the coast. Historian Edward Alpers estimates that the ivory trade in colonial Mozambique in the late sixteenth century could result in the killing of around 1000 elephants a year.³⁴⁹ The depictions of animals from this area provide lots of information on maritime animals, acknowledging the intense relations of that society with the sea, but also concentrating on describing the hunting of elephants.

The consideration of knowledge produced in this colonial and missionary context brings to the surface the relation between science and Empires, or, in other words, the issue of how science is produced through colonial networks. Natural history was not a *naïf* interest on the part of João dos Santos, but an expression of the awareness of its importance to European knowledge about the world in the early modern period. On many occasions, he expresses notions of modern political thought, mostly the ideas of good government. As revealed in the example of D. João de Castro, evoked in the work in a typical use of exemplarity under the notion of *historia magistrae vitae*, a good colonial agent should be eager to consistently gather information about the land, in which the knowledge of fauna and flora was particularly important. These were important elements of cartographic knowledge, essential to governing distant and scarcely-known territories. Pragmatic aspects of those natural depictions' primary use for survival in foreign lands were eating and medical use. The former consisted of a vulnerability of Portuguese presence in fortresses in different parts of the Indian Ocean that depended on the food supply coming from local economies. The latter consisted of the knowledge of maladies and their forms of healing that were

³⁴⁷ David Livingstone, *Missionary travels and research in South Africa, including a sketch of sixteen year's residence in the interior of Africa* (London: J Murray, 1857), 712.

³⁴⁸ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 257-339.

³⁴⁹ Edward Alpers, "Moçambique marítimo (sécs. XIV-XXI)," *Revista de História*, 178 (2019): 16.

basic for surviving in different lands and climates. The knowledge of local diseases and their forms of healing is a typical example of transcultural knowledge production.³⁵⁰

Mermaids and Manatees

Another strong component in natural history treaties in the Friar's narrative is the association between mermaids and manatees. Mermaids and diverse forms of hybrids of women and fish are present in very different cultures, and particularly in European folklore since Ancient times, traversing the Middle Ages. Their persistence in natural history treaties, still in the eighteenth century, are a proof of the continuities with older traditions, like the medieval *bestiaries*, especially during the early modern period. In Europe, sirens “were portrayed in church iconography, in the artwork and architecture of aristocratic homes, commercial wares, handicrafts and in cabinets of curiosities (...) they appeared frequently among the pages of early modern printed texts, were visually represented in illuminated manuscripts and maps and the subject of literary, scientific and religious texts.”³⁵¹ According to Cristina Brito:

“The definition-defying and boundary-crossing mermaid offers a fascinating window into the malleability of early modern concepts such as sex and gender, selfhood and mystery, as well as natural and unnatural. This is similar to the construction of the concept of (early) modern zoology or natural history, where nature and culture were co-players and knowledge production was hybrid and connected.”³⁵²

In reprising the topic of connecting the myth of mermaids to describing mammals that were exotic animals to the Europeans, João dos Santos particularly reveals the literary making of natural history through a travel narrative, and the role of the Ancients, even when they might be incorrect. Probably he refers to *dugong* (name of Malaysian origin), a specific type of mammal from the Indian Ocean that lives near the shore and is currently threatened with extinction due to massive fishing. The Friar declares he very often eats the animal's meat, together with cabbage, when in Sofala, having learned from fishermen of its characteristics and habits. The fish is said to be very similar to humans from the belly to the neck, having arms (but not hands, nor fingers, reminds the author), a deformed face and a mouth full of teeth. Because of such similarities, the Friar considers that

³⁵⁰ Maria Cristina Wissenbach, *Ares e azares da aventura ultramarina: matéria médica, saberes endógenos e transmissão nos circuitos do Atlântico luso-afro-americano. O Império por escrito – formas de transmissão da cultura letrado no mundo ibérico, sécs. XV-XVIII*, eds. Megiani et al. (São Paulo: Intermeios, 2020).

³⁵¹ Cristina Brito, “Connected margins and disconnected knowledge: exotic marine mammals in the making of early modern European natural history,” in *Cross-Cultural Exchange and the Circulation of Knowledge in the First Global Age*, eds. Amélia Polónia et. al., (Porto: CIHCEM, 2018), 104.

³⁵² Brito, “Connected margins,” 105.

these mammals might be the mermaids or tritons that “the ancients *confabulated*.”³⁵³ At this point, the description of the animal is interrupted, giving way to a long digression on the ancient myths and poems about mermaids, reprising classic authors and, particularly, Ulysses’ tale, which is told by the Friar, evoking the episode in which the Greek captain covered his mariners’ ears with wax and tied himself to the mast to avoid being enchanted by the mermaids’ singing. After spending much ink on these tales, the Dominican resumes his description of the animal, asserting that those are all “tales of poets, but the truth is that the mammal from its nature is created and conceived in the sea, just as the other fishes.”³⁵⁴ The tale of the mermaids singing, he considers, might be related to the fact that he learned from fishermen that the fish, when removed from the sea, screams and cries, resembling the crying of a human.³⁵⁵

Cultural Intermediaries

In Sofala, one of the Dominican’s main informants was Rodrigo Lobo, who is described as a “wife of the king,” referring to the African chief in the territory. This term was a translation that indicates the way the Shona used the metaphor of marriage and, above all, of kinship, as a structural element of power relations. That title indicates one who had status, controlled land and had slaves. Rodrigo Lobo is a typical go-between, someone who moved around by way of mediations between the Portuguese and the African worlds. He is described by João dos Santos as someone who knew how to speak the language of the so-called “kaffirs” well. The author acknowledges that Rodrigo Lobo controlled an island upon the Buzi River, where he lived with forty slaves.³⁵⁶ The development of a sociability circuit between Friar João dos Santos and Rodrigo Lobo allowed the Dominican to access the latter’s African network. He went to the island to catechize and baptize his slaves, but also went there for pleasure, because it was a place of “great recreation,” as he put it, going on hunts or animal observations – on these occasions, natural history depictions took place.³⁵⁷

João dos Santos talks about a pig hunt organized by the island’s owner in order to please him. Here we can observe a first movement from Rodrigo Lobo towards the Dominican. The slaves were a necessary and constant presence in the Europeans’ penetration of the African interior, as carriers and for the safety of the trip, because the presence of large animals such as

³⁵³ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 150, 151. Translated. “Eu cuido que estas devem ser as Serêas e os Tritões, que os antigos fingiam (...).”

³⁵⁴ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 153. Translated. “Tudo isto são fingimentos de poetas: mas a verdade é, que o peixe-mulher de sua natureza é gerado e creado no mar, como os demais peixes.”

³⁵⁵ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 153.

³⁵⁶ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 114.

³⁵⁷ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 118.

elephants and rhinoceros could be a threat to a human traveling alone. One of dos Santos' important animal depictions is that of the hippopotamus, which was scarcely known in Europe at the time. He wrote a long chapter to visually describe the animal, resorting to many elements of medieval bestiaries. The animal is depicted as a fierce, scary and admiring animal, bigger than two horses, with short and thick feet, a head the size of three oxen, a big torn mouth full of teeth, with four curved horns coming out of it, two going up, and two going down.³⁵⁸

After this description, the Dominican tells a story that can be used to measure the level of interactions between the Portuguese and nature in this African space. He said that he went for recreation and fishing along the Buzi river with two Portuguese men from the fortress. For that purpose, he says, many slaves came together. They were surprised by a couple of hippopotamuses, which ran toward their group, at which point the slaves that had come with them began to cry and to shoot their arrows, in order to scare them, acknowledging that the situation was very dangerous, as the enormous animal could have trampled them. At this point, the author starts describing the techniques of hunting hippopotamuses, which is said to be very hard and tiresome, but an occasion of great joy for the African hunters, who go on hunting trips in great groups, like the one that he once crossed paths with along the Zambezi river made up of a dozen boats with hunters.³⁵⁹

The presence of enslaved people together with the Portuguese spending time off at the river is an important element of the narrative. Though the slave trade in the Indian ocean is ancient, it was never as massive as the Atlantic slave trade before the nineteenth century. Also, slavery inside African territories responds to different parameters than those in the plantations, which meant different margins of negotiation by enslaved people. The collaborative relationships with enslaved people in the production of knowledge about natural history opens up an interpretive path to try to understand the agency of enslaved people in the production of scientific knowledge. Like the go-betweens, enslaved people were privileged intermediaries to the Europeans in foreign territories, especially those enslaved by religious orders. They could act as translators, guides through the hinterlands, or even as transmitters of knowledge and worldviews. It is known that after rounding the Cape of Good Hope, a Moorish slave captured on the African coast guided Vasco da Gama to India. Among João dos Santos' confessing souls, surely there were the enslaved people of the Dominican order, the Sofala fortress, and the Portuguese, all of whom were subjected to the obligation of confession. We can observe the importance of slaves in the local dynamics of knowledge production in *Ethiopia orientalis* in many passages describing animals.

³⁵⁸ Santos. *Ethiopia orientalis*, 170.

³⁵⁹ Santos. *Ethiopia orientalis*, 173.

In one of those, João dos Santos was again on Rodrigo Lobo's island, sitting at his home, when one of his slaves showed up and invited the friar to watch six lions that were crossing the river, which he said was a feast for the eyes.³⁶⁰ The Dominican hesitated, but having been assured that it was safe, he agreed to tag along. We can observe how the slave identified the author's curiosity about nature. In another passage, the Friar describes an animal called *nbaçara*. In many cases, he offers both European and African names for the animal, in some he gives only a Portuguese name, but, in this case, he offers only the African one. By analysing his depiction, one can understand he is talking about the pangolin. He describes its size, skin and claws used for digging and eating ants. As it was often the case, his depiction moves from external aspects to the inside of the animal. Yet again the cultural mediators appear, capturing the animal, opening and cleaning it and saying if it can or cannot be eaten. Many times, the Dominican confirms or denies the good taste of it. In the case of the pangolin, another interesting piece of information is provided: acknowledging that the animal's stomach was empty, the African hunters that accompanied the Dominican offer an explanation that comes from their ancestors, according to which the animal fed itself only from air and could be seen open-mouthed while facing the wind.³⁶¹ This is only a small example of how African perspectives of the natural world can appear in this source.

Lion Hunt

A more significant one is when, during a hunt promoted by Rodrigo Lobo, someone violated the local African law prohibiting lion hunting, which is explained by the connection between this animal and the royal ancestor, *mbondoro*; this was very risky and could result in the confiscation of his land. But Rodrigo Lobo knew how to manipulate the local cultural grammar well, as we have observed above, to the point where he reached the prestigious position of "wife of the king."³⁶² So he produced a pompous grave to the lion, covering it with fabrics (which was the main trading currency in Africa), and sent it to the Shona chief along with a message saying that he, Rodrigo Lobo, wife of the king, had killed that lion in honour of his husband, because the animal was being discourteous to his wife. According to João dos Santos, the Shona chief received the gift and sent a message saying that it was right to kill the lion because it was being impolite to his wife.³⁶³ This story exemplifies to the Dominican how well Rodrigo Lobo manipulated the kaffir's language, as

³⁶⁰ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 120.

³⁶¹ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 126, 127.

³⁶² Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 114.

³⁶³ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 117.

he put it. Going beyond his interpretation, the data indicate how well this go-between agent understood and manipulated the Shona interpretation of the natural world and the language of their political power. Something that the Dominican acknowledged and is confirmed by later narratives and present-day ethnography is the relation between south-eastern African chiefs and lions. In the Bantu cosmivision, the most important religious entities are the ancestors, which have direct agency over the earthly world; among the Shona monarchies, the dead chief turns into a specific ancestor who shows up like a lion, which is called a *mbondoro*. The *mbondoro* cult lies at the root of Shona political traditions; it is said to have been initiated by Matope, one of the founders of Munhumutapa State.³⁶⁴

Other examples, through the narrative of João dos Santos, can be provided regarding the association of African power and animals, which can open a path to understanding African notions of nature. Brazilian anthropologist Eduardo Viveiros de Castro has pointed out the difference between multinaturalism in the Western cosmivision, and multiculturalism in the Amerindian cosmivision; whereas the Westerners see a world defined by a unity of nature and a variety of cultures, the Amerindians understand a variety of natures and a unified culture. That unity of culture is a unity of spirit that connects the different bodies present in space, human and non-humans, each one characterized by its particular way of acting in the world.³⁶⁵ For our purposes, it is significant how Viveiros de Castro epistemologically incorporates Amerindian perspectivism, translating and validating this way of thinking about the natural world beyond the Western opposition between nature and culture and using it to rethink some principles of anthropology itself as a discipline. The possibility of decoding and reconstructing ways of thinking from an African cultural grammar appears in the work of Friar João dos Santos, for it is the result of encounters and translations between cultures and networks characteristic of contact zones.

In the Central African cosmivision, a core metaphor is one of cure and disease, which worked within an anthropological tradition called the “fortune-misfortune complex.”³⁶⁶ The medical knowledge and its practices were developed by individuals that were specialists in connecting with the spiritual world. When talking about religious knowledge, dos Santos reveals having been in touch with such specialists.³⁶⁷ A characteristic aspect used in Central African therapeutics for combating diseases (which was socially understood: slavery and war could be diseases, and therefore also healed) was the manipulation of poison. This use of poison appears in

³⁶⁴ Mudenge, *A political history*, 44.

³⁶⁵ Eduardo Viveiros de Castro, “Perspectival Anthropology and the Method of Controlled Equivocation,” *Tipiti, Journal of the Society of Anthropology of Lowland South America* 2, (2004).

³⁶⁶ Willy de Craemer, Jan Vansina, and Renée Fox, “Religious movements in Central Africa: a theoretical study,” *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 18, (1976).

³⁶⁷ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 70.

pre-colonial and colonial documentation. Particularly, it was manipulated as an instrument of power by the head of the African state, through their use in ordeals.³⁶⁸ In dos Santos' narrative, significant information is provided in the making of poison, for example, from the crocodile's liver. According to him, one part of liver led to poison, and the other, to an antidote.³⁶⁹ Lots of information on the production of antidotes is provided, under the field of therapeutic knowledge, which was part of natural history. Even if the origin of that knowledge was not provided, we can understand it, by comparing it with other parts of the work where those networks are more explicit. He acknowledges being healed by African healers, and collects information on animals and plants among African interlocutors. It is important to observe that those interlocutors had important margins of negotiation and agency, since they were essential for Europeans to move into those territories. Besides that, African political protocols, including the use of ordeals and poison, are described in the book. The knowledge of those protocols was also essential for the Portuguese presence and trade. For example, the killing of the snake called *ruça inbanga* is forbidden, according to João dos Santos, because its very strong poison was used in the confection of arrows, thus leading to a monopoly of the poison by the chiefs. Additionally, he draws on elements from medieval bestiaries, attributing emblematic meanings to those slaves, depicted as evil-characters.³⁷⁰

Another example of the association of animals with political power is the bird called *curuane*, which is compared to the crane, only much more beautiful since it is almost entirely black, as if it were made of silk, but with a white belly, thus resembling a white mushroom or *sombrero*. This resource for comparisons, as we can observe, is frequent, and other birds are used for describing other parts of the animal, such as its red feathers in the face, that are said to be akin to those of the goldfinch. Due to its beauty, it would be considered by the Africans as the "king of birds" and used as a symbol by various important chiefs in the region.³⁷¹

Layers of Circulation

Concerning the circulation of knowledge through local networks that links the Dominican friar to African informants, it is important to observe the use and incorporation of African vocabulary, mostly Shona, throughout his work. This occurs not only when it comes to naming animals and plants that didn't exist in Europe and were common in that African society, but also in other fields, such as religious knowledge, material culture (for example musical instruments, hunting and

³⁶⁸ John Janzen. *Lemba, 1650-1930: A Drum of Affliction in Africa and the New World* (London: Garland, 1982).

³⁶⁹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 144.

³⁷⁰ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 130.

³⁷¹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 136.

navigating, military), geographic knowledge, trade institutions, among others. When giving toponyms, João dos Santos usually gives both Portuguese-attributed and local names: he registers the local name Zambezi for what the Portuguese called *Cuama rivers* (from Arab name, *Kwama*); also, he gives the name Madagascar to what the Portuguese unanimously called the island of Saint Lourenço. One important passage of the work reveals his understanding of the different dialects of Shona: he says that in Munhumutapa, the Shona language is more politely spoken than elsewhere in that region, because it contains a gracious, soft and whistled sound, very different from what he calls the scratchy sound of Arabic, that sound as if the words are being vomited out of the speaker's mouth, according to his depiction.³⁷² Of course, this statement from friar João dos Santos is full of political meanings, and we cannot unravel them here in each historical layer of this representation. Our goal here is to measure his grasp and level of understanding of the Shona language, in order to better observe the modes of mediation and translation and the role of African interlocutors and go-betweens in the production of knowledge.

We can observe how many African names are incorporated in the description of animals, including a big diversity of fishes and birds. One bird, named *sazy*, is said to feed on wax, often entering the church from Sofala to eat the wax from their candles, being captured there by the sextons for their meat. Another, named *minga*, is said to be similar to the pigeon, and is very fat and tasty. Also on fishes the author offers very precise local denominations: a fish called *macone*, frequently eaten by the locals, is very fresh, but unsavoury; the Dominican says he ate it many times. Another, named *munemune*, has such a strong smell that only locals can eat it. It is important to gauge the use of those terms because João dos Santos' work would be used by cartographers and naturalists throughout the eighteenth and the nineteenth centuries as the most important source on Eastern Africa. The knowledge produced through his African networks would have great influence on the shaping of European knowledge, due to the circulation of his work and his capacity of validating the information provided. Through the work of João dos Santos, for example, many African toponyms entered European cartography. Additionally, naturalists such as Georges Louis Leclerc, the count of Buffon, heavily relied on travel literature in their project classifying the world's nature.³⁷³

³⁷² Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 223.

³⁷³ Buffon, George Louis Leclerc. *Histoire naturelle, générale et particulière, avec la description du Cabinet du Roi* (Paris: Imprimerie Royale, 1749-1767).

Reception

It is important to point out the later trajectory of *Etiópia oriental* in order to gauge its circulation and impact on knowledge production. After the publication in the Dominican Convent of Évora in 1609, we can already observe the first reception, for the author was sent back to Eastern Africa, given that the eleven years that he had spent there were mentioned, in the royal decision from 1611. Another text from 1618, by Francisco Avellar, demonstrates the work's circulation. Also a Dominican friar, he wrote, based on João dos Santos' work, a settlement plan for the Zambezi valley.³⁷⁴ In 1622, significant excerpts from *Etiópia oriental* were translated to Latin by Afonso de Sandoval, a translation that was made available to European erudite circles.³⁷⁵ A few years later, in 1625, it was also partially translated into English, by Samuel Purchas, in his *Hakluytus Posthomus or Purchas his Pilgrims*. Purchas was the successor of Richard Hakluyt, the famous travel-literature-compiler from Elizabethan England. These collections, as well as Giovanni Ramusio's *Navigazione et viaggi*, show the interest early modern Europe had in Portuguese information regarding the unknown world, which was expressed particularly through travel literature. At the end of the seventeenth century there would still be two French editions of João dos Santos would exist: the first published in 1684 by Gaétan Charpy, dedicated to Colbert, and widely circulated; the second one, from 1688, however - which remained an anonymous manuscript, was much more precise than the former, and was kept in the archives of French Ministry of Foreign Affairs.³⁷⁶

In the eighteenth century, despite not being reedited, dos Santos' work was still in use. Historian Júnia Furtado has shown that it was largely used by Enlightenment cartographer Jean Baptiste Bourguignon d'Anville, who accessed many Portuguese sources in collaboration with the Portuguese ambassador in Paris, D. Luís da Cunha, who participated in the negotiations of the border limits between Portuguese and Spanish America, and cultivated a project connecting the African colonies of Angola and Mozambique by land.³⁷⁷ At the end of the eighteenth century and the beginning of nineteenth century, it was also used by Scottish Enlightenment cartographer John Pinkerton, who translated and published some passages of the work in his *General Collection of the Best and most interesting Voyages and Travels in all Parts of the World*. This version was published in London between 1808 and 1814, with the title *History of Eastern Africa: Originally written in Portuguese*

³⁷⁴ Florence Pabiou-Duchamp, "João dos Santos: un dominicain portugais dans le Sud-Est africain" (PhD Diss., University of Paris Sorbonne – Panthéon 1, 2007), 171–73.

³⁷⁵ Ivana Muscalu, "Da boa guerra nasce a boa paz: a expulsão dos portugueses do planalto da Zambézia (1603–1695)," (PhD Diss., University of São Paulo, 2017), 138.

³⁷⁶ Pabiou-Duchamp, "João dos Santos," 173–75.

³⁷⁷ Júnia Furtado, *Quebra-cabeça africano* (Belo Horizonte: Miguelin; Odisséia, 2022).

language by the Reverend Father Joano dos Santos, for the order of St. Domingo, and published in Paris in the year of 1684. The title indicates the use of Gaétan Charpy's version in the translation.³⁷⁸

During the nineteenth century, the work was still consulted by researchers and explorers connected to geography societies, like David Livingstone and John Sutherland in his *Memoirs Respect the Kaffirs, Hottentots and Bosejmans of South Africa* (1845).³⁷⁹ Nevertheless, it was not reprinted, becoming a rare book, sold at elevated prices among bibliophiles and collectors. It would wait until the end of the century to be republished, both in Portuguese and English, in the context of the dispute between these two nations for the colonial division of Africa. The introduction and notes in the Portuguese edition of 1891 are evidence of that political context. Luciano Cordeiro, the editor, was the head of the Portuguese Geography Society and in his introduction, he attacks the greed of the British who want to erase Portuguese rights regarding the map of the "Dark Continent."³⁸⁰ Cordeiro also raises João dos Santos as a hero of Portuguese discoveries and regrets his being forgotten, indicating that at that time only three original editions of the Dominican's work remained available in Portugal. Despite already being used by the English, as Cordeiro's text makes clear, a new English edition was introduced in this context, in 1901, by George McCall Theal, a South-African missionary and British colonial official, in his massive work *Records of South-Eastern Africa* which compiled and translated sources.³⁸¹

In a very different context, another English edition came out in the twentieth century. *Etiópia Oriental* was again partially translated and published in 1962 by Freeman-Greenville in his *The East Africa Coast. Selected Documents from the First to the Earlier Nineteenth Century*. This was the context of the development, in the 1960s, of the History of Africa as an academic discipline. In the *General History of Africa*, published in those years with the support of UNESCO, dos Santos' work is substantially used in the chapters that concern the Eastern African coast and the Zambezi valley and plateau, mostly quoting the translations by McCall Theal and Freeman-Greenville. Portuguese historians would continue to work, even if scantily, with Cordeiro's edition, until 1989, when historian Luís de Albuquerque would edit and republish it in another collection of texts from the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries connected to Portuguese explorations and discoveries. This edition still presented problems such as changes in the order of the chapters and the removal of some passages. Ten years later, though, the first critical edition would appear in 1999, edited by historian Manuel Lobato, sponsored by the National Commission for Celebration of the

³⁷⁸ Pabiou-Duchamp, "João dos Santos," 173.

³⁷⁹ John Sutherland, *Memoirs respect the Kaffirs, Hottentots and Bosejmans of South Africa* (Cape Town: Pike & Philip, 1845).

³⁸⁰ Luciano Cordeiro, ed., *Etiópia Oriental e Varia História de Cousas Notáveis do Oriente* (Lisbon: Biblioteca dos Clássicos Portugueses, 1891), 7.

³⁸¹ George Mc Call Theal, *Records of South Eastern Africa* (Cape Town: C. Stuijk, 1964), 9 vols.

Portuguese Discoveries, which republished a plethora of texts and studies. This is the most recommended edition for research, although it still has some problems, for example the non-modernization of African words and toponyms, instead of the Portuguese ones. Finally, a last edition in French was done in the context of a PhD research project at University of Paris 1 – Panthéon Sorbonne, presented in 2007 by Florence Pabiou-Duchamp. This thesis resulted in another publication in French in 2011, edited by Pabiou-Duchamp, published by the Chandeigne publishing house, in a travel literature collection from the sixteenth to the eighteenth century. In a review of this edition, historian Thomas Vernet pointed out the potentialities of João dos Santos' work, observing that no other source before the end of eighteenth century can offer a such an expressive view on cultural exchanges in that region.³⁸²

³⁸² Thomas Vernet, "Ethiopia orientale. L'Afrique de l'Est et l'océan Indien au XVIe siècle. La relation de João dos Santos (1609)," *Journal des Africanistes sur le pas de Geneviève Calaupe-Griaule* 85 (2011): 460.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is important to observe how the knowledge produced in the work of João dos Santos has reverberated from the time of its publication to present-day historiography. If that which is considered “modern science” originated in the “scientific revolution” of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, when observing the nature of that knowledge and the material conditions of its production, one cannot assume it is a purely Western creation. In reality, that knowledge was produced through transcultural networks. However, it is not enough to identify the role of local informants, as if they were a passive information resource. When looking at the margins of negotiation and the local conditions of European presence in colonial territories, it is possible to identify local forms of agency and how those populations (“subaltern” at the level of representation) imprint their marks on the production of scientific knowledge. This led to hybrid forms of knowledge production, as this paper tried to demonstrate in the work of João dos Santos, where multiple forms of translations, mediations, misunderstandings take place, producing a diverse and heterogenous body of knowledge that is both African and European. While João dos Santos’ work on regional Eastern Africa history is widely known, it was generally used as a source of political history, and sometimes of the history of religion, his natural history descriptions are mostly ignored. This paper’s goal was to bring those accounts to the centre of our analysis, bringing up questions raised by recent perspectives on the history of science. Most importantly, we ought to unravel the many layers of representation contained in the Dominican’s narrative in order to understand the other voices and forms of local engagement contained in that writing.

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